

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF THE METHOD "DIDACTICAL CINQUAIN" IN THE TEACHING OF THE SUBJECT "CHILDREN AND TEENAGE LITERATURE"

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the technology of application of the Didactic Cinquain method, the results achieved, and outlines the perspectives for its future application. The method was implemented with undergraduates of the specialty "Bulgarian Language and History" from the University of Ruse and Vidin Branch, who are studying the discipline "Children and Teenage Literature".

Keywords: Didactic cinquain, Course "Children and Teenage Literature", Bachelors, higher education, creative task.

Introduction

The poetic form *cinquain* (French *cinquain*, English *cinquain*) originated in the early 20th century in the USA. Its creator was the American poet Adelaide Crapsey (1878–1914), who was influenced by Japanese short-form poetry *haiku* and *tanka* and created an original genre [1]. In its original form, the poem consists of five unrhymed stanzas that form a poetic unity. Formally, the cinquain consists of 22 syllables and has the following pyramidal structure of syllables: 2-4-6-8-2.

In the following decades, the poetic form of *the cinquain* became an educational method. The methodology was developed in the USA and is known as *didactic cinquain*. Only the idea of a stanza of five lines has remained of the original conception of the poetic form. The model of didactic cinquain looks as follows:

First verse (the subject of the cinquain): a noun or pronoun.

Second verse: two words – adjective or participle. They describe the attribute of the selected object.

Third verse: three verbs or verbal adverbs describing the characteristic actions of the subject.

Fourth stanza: a four-word phrase/ statement expressing the author's personal attitude toward the subject or object being described.

Fifth verse: a distinct noun characterizing the subject (a synonym), also serving as a conclusion. (For more details on the origin of the cinquain, see [2], [3].

Exposition

Our preliminary studies have shown that didactic cinquain is not widely used in contemporary Bulgarian education, unlike its widespread use in the American and Russian educational systems. It is sporadically used in Bulgarian language teaching at the primary stage of education [4], [5]. Our opinion is that this method has great pre-educational and educational potential and should be applied more often in various subjects at all stages of education, including higher education.

In the academic year 2020–2021, the second-year bachelor students in the specialty "Bulgarian Language and History" from the University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev" and the Vidin Branch, studying in the discipline "Children and Teenage Literature", were offered to create an author's cinquain. 49 undergraduates were involved.

In this paper, we present the technology of the method application, the results achieved, and the outlined perspectives for its further application.

Technology of application of the method "Didactic cinquain"

Preliminary preparation: the teacher prepares a presentation that includes the following components: definition of a cinquain, rules for writing it, examples, the due date for the assignment, ready template¹, suggestions of topics for creating it, and specifies the criteria for evaluation². Once the assignment is specified, the information is sent to the students so that they can have it at their disposal during their preparation.

It is known that not all learners have an affinity for poetry, the creation of a cinquain is characterised as a *creative task rather* than writing a poem. The presentation of the assignment can be done face-to-face or in the process of synchronous or asynchronous distance learning. In each case, a PowerPoint presentation is created for better visualization.

Different themes are proposed and oriented in two main units.

Concepts specific to the discipline of *Children and Teenage Literature*: literature, fairy tale, fable, poem, initiation, short story, riddle, legend, myth, magic, animal, bit, child, adolescent, hero, antagonist, giver, sender.

Common human themes also tied to the discipline: love, family, home, wisdom, kindness, life, beauty, nature, fate, luck, freedom, and adventure.

¹ The special template was developed for convenience and was borrowed from the American methodology.

² Students in the first group are graded on a 6-point scale with a maximum of 15 points and represents an element of their

semester exam. Students in the second group create a synopsis as part of their semester commitments, receive points but they are not included in their overall semester grade.

In implementing the method, we formulated the following didactic and educational tasks.

Didactic tasks:

- ✓ Learning, comprehension, and correct application of parts of speech;
- ✓ Developing information synthesis skills;
- ✓ Enriching language culture and improving vocabulary;
- ✓ Developing creativity;
- ✓ Developing critical thinking;
- ✓ Skills to compose a complete (poetic) text.

Educational tasks:

- ✓ Comprehension and understanding of the concepts of the discipline;

- ✓ Learning a new didactic method.

Results

A total of 53 cinquains were obtained because several learners worked on two different topics of their own volition. The students preferred to write mostly on general human themes, with most texts produced on the themes of *child, freedom* and *love*. Their own themes are also suggested: *car, war, wolf, fairy*. Significantly fewer are the cinquains devoted to the specific concepts of the discipline of *Children and Teenage Literature*: two works on *initiation*, one each on *antagonist, literature, legend* and *hero*. The choice of topics is explicable – since the method is unknown to the learners, they instinctively stick to the more familiar field.

Table 1.

Examples of cinquain creation in the discipline "Children and Teenage Literature"

<p>Common human themes also linked to the discipline</p>	<p>Love Selfless, unique Excites, comforts, inspires When the soul becomes whole Patience</p>
<p>Concepts specific to the discipline "Children and Teenage Literature"</p>	<p>Initiation Symbolic, pagan Separates, dedicates, includes An important ritual for growth and maturation Symbols</p>

As it has become clear, each cinquain is evaluated according to predetermined evaluation criteria. They are as follows. 1. The cinquain is written according to the rules (number of words) – 1-3 points; 2. Content (absence of notional errors and contradictions) – 1-3 points; 3. Literacy (absence of grammatical and punctuation errors); 4. Parts of speech mentioned in the rules are used correctly; 5. Questionnaire completed – 1 point³; 6. Originality of performance – 1-2 points.

The introduction of a scoring system for the evaluation of the cinquains excludes subjectivity. The scores obtained are between 10 (the lowest) and 15 (the highest). The highest number of students scored 14 points. 15 points were obtained by 19 learners.

The tutor gives feedback with brief comments, errors, and points formed based on the specified criteria.

Although at first glance the creation of a cinquain seems easy, mistakes have been made, which we will systematize here.

- ✓ Use of template phrases and sentences: *big world; beautiful, big, unexplainable love; easy/ hard life; warm, cozy home*;

- ✓ Inconsistency of the noun (line 1) with the verbs (line 4) – 5 uses;

- ✓ Repetitions – 5 people;
- ✓ Inappropriate combination of words (*cozy family; biological love; colourful fairy, young child*) – 4 people;

- ✓ Inconsistency of the noun (1 line) with the adjectives/participles – 2 uses;

- ✓ Incorrect use of parts of speech (e.g., in line 5 is used the adjective instead of their noun) – 3 people;

- ✓ Grammatical/ spelling errors – 3 people;

- ✓ Vague phrase – 3 people;
- ✓ The phrase does not comprise of four words (it's longer or shorter) – 2 people;
- ✓ Incorrect linking of a noun with a reflexive verb – 2 people;
- ✓ Missing the personal attitude in the phrase – 1 student;
- ✓ Inappropriate use of inversion (*Two hearts captivated* – "Love") – 1 student;
- ✓ Inappropriate choice of synonyms (*literature – bit*, lines 1 – 5) – 1 student;
- ✓ Choice of ungrammatical words – lives – 1 student;
- ✓ Technical errors – 1 student.

As can be seen from the summary list of errors, they are mainly related to the incorrect use of parts of speech and stylistics. However, we can say that the omissions are not many. To a lesser extent, mistakes were made in the exact execution of the instructions for writing the cinquain.

Although the students are not asked to write a poem as a prerequisite, some of them try to demonstrate originality. Here we present some of the more imaginative phrases: *turns the sage into a dreamy fool; like a black and white film; makes the heart happy; when the soul becomes whole* ("Love"), *happiness for the human eye and soul* ("Beauty"), *gives meaning and strength to life* ("Beauty"); *birth is a mysterious female initiation* ("Initiation"); *gave the bird freedom* ("Freedom").

Generally as a good poem I rate the cinquain of a student from Vidin Branch: the text is executed entirely according to the rules, without mistakes, and the phrase from line 4 is truly poetic.

³ Since the Didactic cinquain method is introduced for the first time in the training of the students of the major

"Bulgarian Language and History", a special questionnaire was developed to find out what is the attitude of the students.

Winter*White, frosty**It snows, it covers, it piles up**I drink tea in the warm hut.**Beautiful!***Perspectives**

The work with the Didactic cinquain method shows that it is very suitable for use in the discipline "Children and Teenage Literature". In the academic year 2021/2022 it was also successfully used in the teaching of other subjects – "New Bulgarian Literature" (3rd year, specialisation "Bulgarian Language and History") and "Legal Language and Style" (1st year, specialisation "Law"). Its use is to be extended to other courses in order to make the results representative.

Conclusion

Analysing the achieved results, we believe that the set didactic and educational tasks have been largely realized. The realized feedback from the learners, obtained through the completed questionnaire⁴, reveals that they liked the creative task. Although few students had written cinquains on concepts specific to the discipline, 25 people said that writing a cinquain helped them in making sense of some of the terms or characteristic themes, and 8 people answered *somewhat*.

Interesting are the answers to the question *What is the usefulness of writing a cinquain for students' learning?* Here we will present the most numerous answers: 10 people think that it develops thinking activity; 8 people – helps to realize creativity, imagination, and creative potential; 2 answers each: additional knowledge; developing poetic skills; developing speech skills and expressive abilities, enriching vocabulary, etc.

It is pleasant that some prospective teachers recognize didactic cinquain as an interesting, useful, and effective method of teaching. Learners felt that it could be successfully applied in secondary school but also saw potential in working with preschool children who would develop their speech. Three respondents said

they recommend the method and would use it with their current and future students.

The application of didactic cinquain in higher education revealed its great educational potential in teaching and showed that it was very well accepted and positively evaluated by students as it was easy to implement, entertaining but also effective.

References

1. Crapsey, Adelaide. Verse. New York, N.Y.: Alfred A. Knopf, 1922 [electronic text]. URL: <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/a/amverse/BAE8954.0001.001?view=toc> (Accessed on 20.10.2022).
2. Душкова, Мира. Синквейн – още една съвременна поетическа форма. – Алманах „Светове“. 40 години средно училище „Възраждане“. Годишно издание на СУ „Възраждане“ – Русе, г. XIX. Русе, 2021, с. 48-50.
3. Душкова, Мира. Синквейн – между средновековната петстишна строфа и съвременната поетико-дидактична форма. Текстът е представен на Международния симпозиум в чест на 60-годишнината на доц. д-р Емил Димитров (Под печат/ To be published).
4. Томаатанасова, Недялка. Радвам се, че си тук... или методи на обучение по БЕЛ в интеркултурната класна стая. URL: <https://www.eduset.net/tools/radvam-se-che-si-tuk-ili-metodi-na-obuchenie-po-bel-v-interkulturnata-klasna-staya> (Accessed on 22.03.2022 г.).
5. Йочева, Калина. Иновативни техники в обучението по български език в началното училище. – В: Доклади от Международната юбилейна конференция на Института за български език „Проф. Любомир Андрейчин“. Част втора. София: Институт за български език при БАН, 2017, с. 164-171.

⁴ The study involved 39 participants out of 49 students enrolled in the Literature for *Children and Teenage Literature* course.